

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D6.1: Large pouch cell and module prototype design & assembly definitions

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Glossary and Abbreviations

ASEI	Artificial solid electrolyte interphase
BOPP	Biaxially oriented polypropylene
C/Al current collector	Carbon-coated aluminium current collector
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
CRM	Critical raw materials
Cu	Copper
EC	Ethylene carbonate
ECU	Electrode Cutting Unit
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
KPI	Key performance indicator
Li-M	Lithium metal
LiBOB	Lithium bis(oxalate)borate
LiFSI	Lithium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide
Li salts	Lithium salts
MEK	Methyl Ethyl Ketone
MFCA	Material flow cost accounting
MSX	Milestone X
NMC	Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxides
NMP	N-Methyl-Pyrrolidone
PM	Particulate matter
PO	Project officer
PVDF-HFP	Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene)
SoC	State of charge
SOX	Strategic objective X
SPE	Solid polymer electrolyte
SSB	Solid-state battery
SSE	Solid-state electrolyte
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

In this document, all efforts done in designing 1 Ah and 10 Ah cells using the optimised values for cell components and process parameters, which were performed during M19 to M25 in WP 6, are presented. This includes i) definitions and designs of 1Ah and 10 Ah pouch cells and ii) cell holder (jig) design for both 1 and 10 Ah pouch cells. It should be noted that the details used to design the initial modules are also included in the eco-design deliverable of D2.2, which is supposed to be finalised in T6.4 later.

In the first part, the parameters used for the cathode, solid electrolyte layer and lithium metal anode are fully described for both 1 Ah and 10 Ah pouch cells. Then these parameters are discussed regarding their economic and environmental influences. In the second part of D6.1, the process of optimising the cell holder design regarding its effectiveness on pressure distribution is investigated, and finally, its optimised version is introduced.

1. Introduction

To meet the KPIs defined in the SPINMATE project, careful design of all cell components and their target properties are necessary. This design is also closely related to the capabilities of the equipment that is used for the different process steps of the electrodes and cell production. Task 6.1 aims to develop these designs based on the specifications and requirements derived in WP 2 as well as the economic and environmental parameters from WP 8. Therefore, in deliverable 6.1, the cell design for small (single layer and 1 Ah) and large (10 Ah) pouch cells was fixed and the details on this are shown in the following sections. In addition, the mechanical pressurised cell holders (jigs) were designed in task 6.1 to do the cell testing under defined pressures.

2. Pouch cell design definitions

2.1 Pouch format cells requirements

Pilot line specifications

The coating process for the NMC811 will be managed by a syringe pumping system that follows the detailed recipe initially optimised in the WP3. Each batch will involve double-sided coating, with approximately 300 ml of slurry applied per side. The coating will be precisely dispensed through a 300 mm industrial slot die, shimmed to achieve a 130 mm width, which aligns with the SPINMATE project's requirements - Specifically, a 130 mm wide coating on a 180 mm wide foil.

Post-coating, the slurry will be subjected to a drying process using two in-line ovens, each extending one meter in length. These ovens will operate within a temperature range optimised for the specific slurry composition, ensuring efficient drying and solvent evaporation. The exhaust system will be carefully balanced at both the inlet and outlet to maintain a safe environment and to enhance the removal of residual solvents from the coating.

Following drying, the electrode material will undergo in-line calendering, which provides precise control of the thickness down to the micron level. The calendering rolls are capable of applying up to 20 kN of pressure on each side, a critical factor in achieving the desired energy density and ensuring that the NMC811 electrode meets the project's performance criteria.

The same slot-die coater will be utilised to produce the solid-state electrolyte (SSE). The production of the SSE is first developed at ARKEMA's facility, moving from lab-scale to pilot-line scale before being transferred to a larger production environment. This stage poses significant challenges due to the delicate nature of the SSE slurry and the absence of a supporting foil during processing. To address this, there are two potential strategies: processing a self-standing membrane or utilising a temporary support membrane.

Operationally, all processes will be conducted at speeds ranging from 0.1 to 1 meter per minute, which is adequate to meet the project's production volume requirements. A critical challenge in this process is fine-tuning the coating parameters and optimising the slurry formulation. Once these parameters are fully established, the production can proceed efficiently, ensuring timely project completion. All battery manufacturing processes in the ABEE's pilot line are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of the process described above. From left to right: Unwinder, coating area, oven 1 & 2, calendaring unit, rewinder.

The anode part of the pilot line is described lower in this document through “Lithium metal anode’s parameter definition”.

Economic and environmental parameters

The economic and environmental objectives to be achieved in SPINMATE focus on the “reduction of the manufacturing costs and energy consumption of around 15% and 10%, respectively” and the “reduction of 20% of the carbon intensity in terms of CO₂/kWh”, as mentioned in the strategic objective 3 (SO3). These parameters are further specified in SO4 and SO5, where, for the final SSB technology, the project aims for a “decrease of CO₂ emissions (<100 kg CO₂/kWh)” and “Low-cost configuration <75 euro/kWh”, respectively. As such, these parameters, alongside other relevant environmental parameters, were quantified for the initial designs (for the 1 Ah and the 10 Ah cells) in order to obtain the current cost and environmental performance and support the continuing design developments of the SPINMATE SSB technology to achieve these objectives by the end of the project.

The cost (€/cell) and the global warming potential (GWP, in kg CO₂ eq/cell) were calculated for the initial cell design assessment. To better understand the main environmental impacts of the SSB cells, other environmental parameters were considered to avoid impact shifting. The parameters considered are listed and briefly described in Table 1.

In assessing the economic aspects, only the production cost of the SSB cell was taken into account, as the process is currently on a lab scale. Costs of products produced at a lab scale can significantly differ from those at an industrial scale due to variations in energy usage and the concept of economy of scale. Lab-scale processes typically consume less energy due to the many manual steps involved. Additionally, the energy consumed throughout the process is often difficult to measure, leading to it being frequently excluded from consideration, as in the current study. Moreover, industrialized processes tend to optimize material usage, leading to reduced wastage and lower costs as the quantity of the final product increases, in other words, economy of scale.

The results from evaluating the costs using the provided lab-scale data have limitations. Parameters that may consider comparisons with current technologies, forecasting values, and upscaling the process based solely on the data provided can lead to misleading conclusions. Therefore, no additional parameters were considered in this analysis.

The quantification of the economic parameter was based on the Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) methodology, which tracks materials and energy flows and quantifies their associated costs. For the environmental parameters, the quantification was conducted using the software SimaPro V9.5.0.0.¹ with the ReCiPe v1.1 impact method, and the database used was ecoinvent v3.9.1². The results were presented in ReCiPe Midpoint (H) v1.08.

Table 1: Description of the economic and environmental parameters.

Cost parameter	Description
Production cost of the SSB cell [€/cell]	Total material and energy expenses associated with the production of a single SSB cell, measured in euros.
Environmental parameter	Description
Global Warming	The global warming potential, as detailed in the IPCC 2013 report ³ , quantifies the cumulative increase in infrared radiative forcing attributed to a greenhouse gas (GHG) over a 100-year timeframe, employing the Hierarchist perspective. This potential is expressed in kilograms of CO ₂ equivalents.
Fine particulate matter (PM) formation	The intake fraction of PM _{2.5} is expressed in terms of kilogram equivalents of PM _{2.5} .
Mineral resource scarcity	The excess ore capacity is expressed in terms of kilogram equivalents of copper.
Fossil resource scarcity	The fossil fuel potential, calculated using a higher heating value, is measured in units of kilogram oil equivalents.
Water consumption	The volume of freshwater used is expressed in cubic meters.

The environmental and economic quantification was performed at the material level. The parameter quantification is derived from primary data provided by partners. The data considered and provided is presented in Table 2.

¹ PRé Sustainability, “SimaPro database manual Methods library,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://simapro.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/DatabaseManualMethods.pdf>

² M. A. J. Huijbregts et al., “ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level,” *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 138–147, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y.

³ IPCC, 2013: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp

Table 2: Data considered for quantifying the economic and environmental parameters.

Cell component	Material	1 Ah cell	10 Ah cell
Cathode	C/Al current collector	□□	□□
	NMC811	□□	□□
	Carbon	□□	□□
	Catholyte	□	□
	NMP	=	=
Solid electrolyte	Polymers	□□	□□
	Plasticizer	□□	□□
	Solvent	=	=
	Li salts	□□	□□
Anode	Lithium metal	□□	□□
	Protective layer	□□	□□
	Cu current collector	□□	□□

The results are presented in the section 2.2 for the 1 Ah cell and in the section 3 for the 10 Ah cell.

The NMP and the solvent were excluded from consideration due to challenges in accurately quantifying their inputs. According to the project partners, the quantities of these materials may vary depending on the specific case.

2.2 Defining 1 Ah pouch cell design

Cathode's parameter definition

As already described in D3.1, the cathode formulation optimised in WP3 contains a ca. 30 vol% of catholyte and 81.4 wt% of cathode active material (NMC811 T81RX from Targray, as agreed with the rest of partners as well as with the PO during the meeting on 30.01.24; However, in the future, the NMC811 from CPT will be used for the cathode manufacturing of 1 Ah and 10 Ah pouch cells). This cathode was upscaled (1 kg batch) at the CID pilot plant (CP488) to prepare the stock of one-side coated positive electrodes with the size of 5 x 6 cm² for single-layer pouch cell assembly purposes (MS5). In the case of 1 Ah pouch cells, double-sided cathodes need to be prepared with a loading capacity higher than 4.0 mAh/cm² to achieve the expected KPIs of the project for the 10 Ah Gen 4b SSB cells (gravimetric and volumetric energy densities of 450 Ah/kg and 1200 Wh/l, respectively). The specifications of cathodes for both cell configurations are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Cathode specifications for single layer and 1 Ah pouch cells.

Cathode parameter	Features	
	Single layer pouch cell	1 Ah pouch cell
Formulation (wt%)	NMC811 (81.4) / C45 (4.5) / catholyte (14.1)	
Current collector (µm)	Carbon-coated aluminum foil (14)	
Process	Roll-to-roll	
Coating	Single-sided	Double-sided
Loading (mAh/cm ²)	2.57 - 2.65	>4.0
Thickness (µm)	67 - 77	>110 (one side)

Density (g/cm ³)	2.57 - 2.97	>3.0
Dimensions (mm)	50 x 60	

Solid electrolyte layer’s parameter definition

As already described in D3.1, the solid electrolyte optimised in WP3 is composed of a gel electrolyte impregnated in a porous PP separator (Celgard type). The gel electrolyte includes a polymer, a plasticiser and a lithium salts. The final solid electrolyte composite is a self-standing film with a thickness of 50-70 µm and a high conductivity of 1.3 mS/cm at 25 °C. The composite film is stored in between two protective PET liners.

Lithium metal anode’s parameter definition

ABEE is responsible for producing lithium metal anodes through a roll-to-roll process. This method involves depositing a micron-thick layer of lithium metal onto a copper current collector using high-temperature thermal evaporation. While this initial coating creates a basic lithium metal anode, ABEE enhances its performance by applying an Artificial Solid Electrolyte Interface (ASEI)/protective layer. The ASEI, a nanoscale coating of inorganic materials like AlO_x, LiF, or Li₃N, is deposited onto the lithium layer through magnetron sputtering. This crucial step significantly extends battery life and improves overall performance. Both the lithium coating and ASEI deposition occur sequentially in a high-vacuum environment (approximately 10⁻⁵ Torr) to ensure optimal coating quality. The foil is maintained under constant tension throughout the process. Once the sputtering process is complete, the coated foil is carefully wound onto a roll with BOPP interleaves to prevent lithium-to-lithium contact. The general overview of the ABEE’s Li-metal anode coater is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Li-metal and ASEI coating system configuration in the Gen 0 instrument installed in ABEE’s dry room facility.

The subsequent stage involves electrode cutting. An automated Electrode Cutting Unit (ECU) precisely punches out electrodes from the coated aluminium and copper rolls according to specified dimensions. The cut electrodes are then meticulously placed into storage trays by a pick-and-place system. Finally, these electrodes are transferred to a stacking machine where anodes and cathodes are layered alternately to form the battery's core component. This detailed process highlights ABEE's advanced manufacturing capabilities in producing high-performance lithium metal anodes for next-generation batteries.

Quantification of economic parameters for a 1 Ah cell

The costs for producing a 1 Ah cell were calculated using MFCA principles, focusing on the expenses related to the materials and energy used during production. In this case, energy costs were not included due to insufficient data, and the analysis concentrated solely on the materials involved in three specific production steps: cathode production, anode production, and electrolyte production.

Besides that, other considerations include:

- Some material prices were provided in USD and needed to be converted to EUR using the 2023 average exchange rate of 0.924 USD/EUR⁴;
- Waste generated during the process was not included in the assessment due to lack of data;
- The costs of the NMP and solvent components, as indicated in Table 2, could not be calculated because of difficulties in quantifying their inputs. According to the project partners, the quantities may vary for each specific case, and, as a result, there are no associated costs to their inputs.

The total production costs for the 1 Ah cell amount to 29.47 €, with its distribution being illustrated in Figure 3. The cathode production step is the major contributor to the total costs, accounting for more than 70%. In this step, both the NMC811 and the catholyte are introduced in the system, with the NMC811 being responsible for more than 40% and catholyte responsible for around 20-30% of the total costs.

The NMC811 is classified as a critical material, meaning that it is considered to have a certain level of supply risk and economic importance, resulting in high demand and high prices⁵. In its production process on a lab scale, the utilisation of high-purity air, such as Oxygen 5.0, along with the lack of optimisation in the use of materials, makes it even more expensive, justifying the high contributions to the costs. The catholyte, on the other hand, has a high cost due to the complexity of its synthesis and the level of purity required for the materials used in its production. The specialised and niche market for the catholyte also influences the high prices of this material⁶.

⁴ Exchange-rates, "US Dollar (USD) To Euro (EUR) Exchange Rate History for 2023," 2024, Accessed: Jun. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.exchange-rates.org/pt/historico/usd-eur-2023>

⁵ European Commission, "Critical raw materials," 2022, Accessed: Jul. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en

⁶ T. J. S. Schubert, "Commercial Production of Ionic Liquids," 2020, Accessed: Jan. 03, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-35245-5_8

The second major contributor is anode production, which is responsible for 20-30% of the total costs. In this, the Li metal is the main contributor within the step, accounting for more than 20% of the total costs. This component is also classified as a critical material, and as mentioned, its typically high prices justify its contribution.

It is important to note that the process, once it is upscaled, will have different costs, both because of optimisations of the process and materials used – known as economy of scale –, and different intensities of energy consumption⁷. In the case of the cathode, particularly, the costs will probably also be reduced due to the more efficient use of high-purity air when producing NMC811.

1 Ah cell production - cost analysis

Figure 3: Cost analysis of the production of 1 Ah cell (FU: 1 cell).

Quantification of environmental parameters for a 1 Ah cell

The environmental parameters are quantified in this subsection to evaluate the environmental impact of the 1 Ah pouch cell. This analysis contributes to a better comprehension of the cell's environmental impact. The analysis was performed at the material level, not including energy manufacturing consumptions or waste generation for 1 Ah cell.

Figure 4 presents the results by cell component: cathode, electrolyte, and anode and the materials comprising each component are also included. It has to be noted that a suitable match for one of the lithium salts could not be identified in the Ecoinvent database or found in the literature. Consequently, it was excluded from this study. Furthermore, the usage of this material was minimal, so it was not anticipated to have a representative environmental impact.

⁷ L. Mauler, F. Duffner & J. Leker, "Economies of scale in battery cell manufacturing: The impact of material and process innovations," 2021, Accessed: Jul 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116499>

Additionally, NMP and the solvent were excluded from consideration due to difficulties in precisely quantifying their inputs.

Figure 4: Impact on the environmental parameters of the different cell components for a 1Ah cell unit in percentage (%) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

Figure 4 shows that the electrolyte is the main impact contributor in almost all environmental parameters (with the exception of mineral resource scarcity) where its contributions range from approximately 60% to 86%. This result was mainly due to the polymer, which contributed around 60-86% of the total environmental impact.

In the mineral resource scarcity, the cathode was the main impact contributor, contributing approximately 75% of the overall impact. This result was mainly attributed to the NMC811 active material, which contributed to 69% of the impact. The use of materials such as nickel and cobalt within this component was the dominant driver of this result. The electrolyte constituted the second most significant contributor to this impact category, accounting for 24% of the overall score. The binder was identified as almost the sole contributor to this impact within the electrolyte component (23,9%).

Furthermore, the cathode emerged as the second main impact contributor across the remaining impact categories, with contributions between 13-39%. The NMC811 and binder materials were the main responsible for these impacts. Specifically, NMC811 was the dominant contributor to fine particulate matter formation and water formation, accounting for 21% and 31% of the respective parameters. Alternatively, the binder was the main impact contributor to global warming and fossil resource scarcity, with approximately 12% contributions to each.

The anode was the third main impact contributor, with contributions below 1% in all environmental parameters. The Cu current collector was the main responsible for impacts in particulate matter formation, mineral resource scarcity, and water consumption, contributing between 0.027% and 0.786%. Conversely, lithium metal was the main contributor to global warming and fossil resource scarcity, accounting for between 0.034% and 0.062% of these respective parameters. The impact on the anode was not representative of the electrolyte and the cathode. This is related to the mass of the anode used in the cell, which was significantly lower than the electrolyte and the cathode.

3. Defining 10 Ah pouch cell design

To determine the energy density of individual cells, we utilised the component dimensions specified by the ABEE standard for 10 Ah pouch cells. These particular cells were chosen as a representative model for our calculations. The exact measurements of each cell component, along with the number of layers comprising the cell structure, are detailed in the accompanying sections below. However, before we jump to the detailed parameters, Table 4 will help us understand the dimensions of the 10 Ah cell components format for the SPINMATE project.

Table 4: Cell dimension for the 10 Ah cells format.

Parameters	Unit	Anode	Cathode	Solid polymer electrolyte
Length	mm	126	124	131
Width	mm	98	96	103
Single-side coated layer	N°	0	2	24
Double-side coated layer	N°	12	11	0

Cathode, solid polymer electrolyte, and Li-metal anode parameter definition

Recipe-wise, the 10 Ah pouch cells will be a dimension-upgraded version of the 1 Ah pouch cells explained in the previous section. The formulation from CID, NMC811/C45/catholyte 81.3/4.5/14.1 wt.%, will be directly used, produced with a roll-to-roll process in double-sided coating form. Moreover, for the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE), the formulation will follow the successful lab trials from ARKEMA, Polymer/plasticiser/Salt1/Salt2 20/70/8/2 wt.%. For the anode, ABEE's Li-metal anode coated on the Cu will manage to reach the thickness range of 10-20 microns to fulfil the battery performance KPIs for the SPINMATE project. The detailed parameters are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Cell dimension for the 10 Ah cells format.

Parameters	Unit	Value		
		Cathode	SPE	Anode
Unit cell ^{*)} range	N°	5-8		
Coating type	-	Double-sided	Impregnated Celgard	Double-sided
Thickness range	µm	150-250	50-70	10-20
Cell volume	cm ³	~37		
Weight	g	~97		
Capacity loading	mAh/cm ²	~10	-	-
Mean voltage	V	~3.8		

Specific energy	Wh/kg	~450
Energy density	Wh/L	~1200

**) : A single-unit cell calculation consists of a single double-coated cathode, two layers of solid polymer electrolytes, and two single-sided Li-metal anodes.*

To perform a comprehensive design for the pouch cell and accurately calculate its final energy density, it is crucial to incorporate the specifications of both the tabs and the pouch itself into the model. These components significantly contribute to the overall mass and volume of the cell, which directly impacts the energy density calculations. Tabs, essential for electrical connection, and the pouch, serving as the cell's protective enclosure, must be meticulously defined. Their dimensions, materials, and weights are integral to the overall cell characterisation. By including detailed parameters for these components, the precision and reliability of the energy density calculations are significantly enhanced.

Table 6 and Table 7 provide the necessary specifications for both tabs and the pouch respectively.

Table 6: Parameters of the tabs for 10 Ah cells.

Tab parameters	Unit	Anode	Cathode
Materials	-	Ni	Al
Length	mm	20	20
Width	mm	30	30
Tab weight	mg/cm ²	13.9	4.7

Table 7: Pouch parameters for 10 Ah cells

Pouch parameters	Unit	Value
Length	mm	158
Width	mm	124
Wall thickness	mm	0.15
Total mass	g/cm ²	0.05

Quantification of economic parameters for a 10 Ah cell

Continuing the cost analysis considering the MFCA methodology, the 10 Ah cell production analysis is illustrated in Figure 5. Just like in the 1 Ah cell, the 10 Ah cell excluded the energy-related costs because of a lack of data, focusing solely on the material flows throughout the production process. Other considerations that are also in common with the 1 Ah cell production are the following:

- Some of the material costs, initially presented in USD, required conversion to EUR, using the average exchange rate for 2023, established at 0.924 USD/EUR⁴;
- The analysis does not include the waste produced throughout the operation because of unavailability of data;
- As shown in Table 2, the expenses associated with the components NMP and the solvent could not be determined due to difficulties in quantifying their inputs. Because of that, no associated costs have been considered for these elements.

The total cost for producing a 10 Ah cell is 83.16 €. The results closely relate to those observed in 1 Ah cell production, in which, despite the higher quantities of each material used, the proportions remained almost the same. Consequently, the major contributor to the costs is the cathode production, accounting for more than 70% of the costs, with the NMC811 (more than 40% of the total costs) and the catholyte (between 20 and 30% of the total costs) as the main responsible.

As explained previously, NMC811 has high costs because of its classification as a critical material and the need for high-purity air paired with a non-optimized production process⁵. The catholyte, on the other hand, has high costs because of the complexity of its synthesis, together with the level of purity of materials needed, amplified even more by the highly specialised market in which it is inserted⁶.

The second major contributor, also aligned with what was observed in the 1 Ah cell production, is the anode production, which is responsible for 20-30% of the total costs. The Li metal is the input of this step that most contribute to the total costs (more than 20%), which happens because of its classification as a critical material.

Again, it is important to consider that the present process is on a lab-scale and, when upscaled, will have different costs. The economy of scale will take place, with costs reducing because of optimisations of the production process as the output increases⁷. At the same time, though, energy costs will probably increase for the more intense energy consumption a bigger scale demands typically. For the cathode, one of the effects of the upscaling will be on the NMC811 with the more efficient use of high-purity air, reducing its costs.

10 Ah cell production - cost analysis

Figure 5: Cost analysis of the production of 10 Ah cell (FU: 1 cell).

Quantification of environmental parameters for a 10 Ah cell

This subsection presents a quantitative assessment of key environmental parameters to evaluate the environmental performance of the 10 Ah pouch cell. The analysis provides insights into the cell's overall environmental impact.

Figure 6 presents the environmental impacts of each cell component: cathode, electrolyte, and anode, including their constituent materials. One of the Li salt materials was excluded from the analysis due to the absence of suitable data within the Ecoinvent database and the available literature. It is important to note that this study focused on material-level impacts and did not encompass energy consumption during manufacturing or waste generation for the 10 Ah cell.

Figure 6: Impact on the environmental parameters of the different cell components for a 10 Ah cell unit in percentage (%) – ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H).

The results are similar to those observed in the production of 1 Ah cells, where, despite the increased quantities of materials used, the relative proportions remained nearly unchanged.

Figure 6 illustrates that the electrolyte predominantly influences most environmental parameters, except mineral resource scarcity. Its environmental impact on these parameters ranges from 69% to 86%.

This significant impact is primarily attributed to polymers, which account for 60-86% of the environmental burden. In the category of mineral resource scarcity, the cathode emerges as the main contributor, responsible for roughly 75% of the total impact. This result is mainly due to the NMC811 active material, which contributes 69% to the impact. The use of materials such as nickel and cobalt in this component is the main driver of this outcome. The electrolyte is the second most significant contributor in this category, representing 24% of the overall impact. Polymers are almost the sole contributor to the electrolyte component, accounting for 23.9% of the impact.

Furthermore, the cathode is identified as the second main impact contributor across the remaining parameters, with contributions ranging from 13% to 39%. The principal materials responsible for these impacts are NMC811 and polymers. NMC811 is the dominant contributor to fine particulate matter formation and water formation, accounting for 21% and 31% of the respective impacts. On the other hand, polymers are the main contributor to global warming and fossil resource scarcity, contributing approximately 12% to each category.

The anode is identified as the third primary impact contributor, with contributions below 1% across all environmental parameters. The Cu current collector is the main contributor to impacts in particulate matter formation, mineral resource scarcity, and water consumption, with contributions ranging from 0.027% to 0.786%. In contrast, Li-M is the main contributor to global warming and fossil resource scarcity, accounting for 0.034% to 0.062% of these respective impacts.

4. Design definition of mechanical cell holder (jig)

Solid-state batteries need a certain external pressure to work properly. The cathode active material, as well as the lithium metal anode, experience volume changes during charging and discharging, which can be in the range of several micrometers for multilayer cells⁸. Compared to a liquid electrolyte, which can infiltrate the porous structure of the electrode and wet the active materials surface, solid electrolytes cannot compensate for the volume changes and, therefore, need a constant external pressure to prevent contact loss of the different cell components. This can be achieved by a pressurised cell holder (jig) that can apply an external mechanical compression force on the pouch cell.

4.1 Jig design for 1 Ah pouch cells

The simplest setup would be a system with a fixed compression at the beginning of the cell testing – e.g. by two parallel plates fixed by screws that are tightened before the cycling tests (Figure 7a). The largest drawback of such a cell holder is that the breathing of the cell is not compensated. This results in an increase and decrease of the cell pressure depending on the SoC and may distort the results because the pressure in the charged stage is different than in the discharged state.

Figure 7: a) Simple pouch cell compression system by two parallel plates fixed by 4 screws (CID). b) Spring-based cell holder for constant pressure application on pouch cells (old version of TUBS, jig v1.0).

⁸ A. Aufschläger, S. Kücher, L. Kraft, F. Spingler, P. Niehoff, A. Jossen, “High precision measurement of reversible swelling and electrochemical performance of flexibly compressed 5Ah NMC622/graphite lithium-ion pouch cells,” *Journal of Energy Storage*, Volume 59, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2022.106483

In another former project, TUBS developed a cell holder (jig) for pouch cells in which the pressure on the two parallel plates is applied by a centered spring (Figure 7b). This enables the application of much more constant pressure on the cell independent from the SoC of the cell. It consists of three plates of 10 mm thick aluminium with an 80 x 160 mm size connected by rods at the 4 edges. The middle plate is movable and can be screwed up using a hexagon nut to place the pouch cell in the center of the jig. By loosening the centered hexagonal screw, the middle plate moves down on the cell, and the pressure from the spring is applied.

To adjust the applied pressure on the cell, spacers/washers can be used to change the displacement of the spring. With the known spring characteristics from the manufacturer (Figure 8), the force can be calculated and with the area of the cell, the cell pressure can be calculated, too. For a cell size of the monolayer and 1 Ah cells of 50 x 60 mm², pressures up to about 1500 kPa can be realised with this setup, which is well in the range needed for the testing of polymer SSBs.

Figure 8: Spring characteristic of the compression spring used in the jigs from TUBS (spring type: D-339T-10, Gutekunst + Co.KG Federnfabriken, Germany).

TUBS sent one of these jigs (jig v1.0) to each partner to test the usability and check the pressure homogeneity. As described in the next section, the pressure distribution was not homogeneous enough, and improvements of the jig were necessary.

Experiments carried out to find associated problems with initial jig design

The jig v1.0 design provided by TUBS was evaluated by CID using a pressure sensitive paper (Fujifilm prescale LLLW). This material is a single-use, pressure-sensitive film that measures pressure ranging from 200 to 600 kPa through peak pressure snapshots, capturing a pressure profile via a colour scale and revealing pressure distribution. Thus, CID could estimate that the pressure applied with the jig v1.0 was not homogeneous, obtaining an irregular pressure distribution all around the cell surface after applying ~ 300 kPa by adding 6 spacers (thickness = 1 mm, $\varnothing_{\text{ext}} = 18$ mm) between the upper plate and the spring (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Pressure distribution of jig v1.0 revealed in a pressure-sensitive paper after applying ~ 300 kPa for 2 min at 25°C , over PSP_04 cell after cycling.

As this applied pressure was in the lowest limit of detection of the paper, CID decided to repeat the experiment but increase the number of spacers. At that moment, CID possessed spacers with 2 mm thickness and 23 mm of external diameter (\varnothing_{ext}), and the experiments performed were a) with $6_{\text{TUBS}}+1_{\text{CID}}$ spacers, or b) with 4_{CID} spacers, to apply in both cases ~ 400 kPa of pressure and compare the pressure distribution registered by the paper (Figure 10). The main conclusion extracted from this experiment was that the higher the \varnothing_{ext} of the spacer is, the more homogeneous pressure distribution is obtained.

Figure 10: Pressure distribution of jig v1.0 revealed in a pressure sensitive paper after applying ~400 kPa during 2 min at 25°C, over PSP_04 cell after cycling.

However, the lack of homogeneity in the pressure distribution remained, probably due to a misalignment of the plates derived from the tilting of the guiding rails and not very uniform thickness of the pouch cell.

Proposed solutions to ensure homogenous pressure distribution

To overcome the described pressure inhomogeneity, the existing jig construction has been adjusted after feedback from all partners (jig v2.0). This adjustment includes mainly 4 different adaptations to reach a better compression of the cell during cycling:

- Increase the thickness of all plates from 10 to 15 mm to prevent bending
- Implement linear ball bearings to guide the movable plate along the rods and prevent clamping by tilting the middle plate
- Grind/polish the surface of the plates in contact with the pouch cell
- Use spacers with larger outer diameter

The technical construction drawings have been updated accordingly, and the new jig is shown in Figure 11a. Afterwards, the workshop of the Institute of Particle Technology (TUBS) has built a prototype of the newly designed jig (Figure 11b) to test if the changes improve the pressure homogeneity. The prototype was sent to CID for evaluation of the pressure distribution.

Figure 11: a) CAD drawing and b) prototype of the newly designed jig v2.0 from TUBS.

The newly designed jig v2.0 prototype was evaluated by CID, with the pressure-sensitive paper and a real single-layer pouch cell after cycling as well as a dummy cell, to avoid the cell inhomogeneities affecting the pressure distribution.

3 spacers (2mm thickness, 23 mm \varnothing_{ext})

Figure 12: Pressure distribution of jig v2.0 revealed in a pressure sensitive paper after applying ~ 300 kPa during 2 min at 25°C , over (a) a dummy cell (0.7 mm thickness) or (b) PSP_07 cell after cycling (0.5 mm thickness).

In the case of the dummy cell, the pressure distribution registered by the paper was more homogeneous all around the surface than in the case of the PSP_07 cell. Then, as mentioned before, the pressure distribution seemed to be correlated with the homogeneity of cell thickness. Finally, after comparing these results with the previous ones with jig v1.0, CID concluded that the pressure distribution was much more homogeneous with this new jig v2.0.

When the improvement in terms of pressure homogeneity of the prototype compared to the older jig version was confirmed, the consortium agreed on the number of jigs each partner needed. This is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Number of jigs required by each partner, including shipping weight.

Partner	Required no. of jigs	Total weight (kg)
CID	6	~ 20
CICe	6	~ 20
IREC	6	~ 20
ABEE	2	~ 7
CEA	2	~ 7
TME	2	~ 7
ISCF	4	~ 13
TUBS	5	~ 16

The initial idea was to contact a manufacturer to produce the jigs for the whole SPINMATE consortium. After internal consultation with the metal workshop of the Institute for Particle Technology (TUBS), they had the capacity to produce the jigs without an external manufacturer to save some money. The production was finished in the middle of July 2024, and the shipment for most of the jigs was arranged for the second half of July to start the single-layer pouch cell experiments before the summer holidays (closing time) of some of the partners. Each partner commissioned a parcel service to pick up the jigs at TUBS for delivery, and the first cell tests were started at the end of July 2024.

4.2 Jig design for 10 Ah pouch cells

The larger cell formats for the 10 Ah pouch cells also need a larger cell holder for cycling tests. Therefore, different ideas were discussed in the consortium. Several springs could be used to apply corresponding pressure, but the disadvantage would be an inhomogeneous pressure distribution if there are (manufacturing-related) differences in the spring parameters between the different springs. The spring characteristics are shown in Figure 13. That would make it necessary to measure the pressure and “calibrate” each jig for different pressures, which is time-consuming and not feasible.

Figure 13: Spring characteristic of the compression spring planned to be used for the 10 Ah jigs that will be produced at the end of 2024 (spring type: D-450, Gutekunst + Co.KG Federnfabriken, Germany).

As discussed in the consortium, the best and most practicable solution will be to stick to the design of the 1 Ah jig and increase the size to fit the large 10 Ah cells. To reach pressures in the same range as the small cells (around 300 kPa), the spring must be replaced by one with a higher constant to apply higher forces. With a 10 Ah cell size of around 13.500 mm², a force of at least 4 kN is necessary. A possible spring to fulfil this requirement is shown in *Figure 13*. The manufacturing of the large cells will be done in task 6.4 starting in M28 (Nov. 2024), and the cell testing in task 7.2 in the last project year. Therefore, the production of the large jigs is planned to start at the end of 2024.

5. Conclusions

Careful design of the battery cells is crucial for upscaling the battery production from small lab-scale cells to larger format cells or even modules. The electrode and cell format strongly depends on the equipment used for the production, namely the coating line specifications as well as the stacking and assembly machines. The material parameters (e.g. capacity of the NCM, thickness of the foils, etc.) play another critical role in determining the cell design.

For the 10 Ah cells, the electrode formats and cell design are mainly influenced by the pilot line equipment used for production. Roll-to-roll processes are inevitable for both the electrodes and the separator layers. This report gives parameters of the cell components, including pouch foil, tabs, etc.

The large-scale double-sided wet coating of the composite cathodes will be done by a roll-to-roll process on an ABEE pilot coating line with a 130 mm slot-die coating width on a 180 mm Al foil. Afterwards, the coated slurries will be dried and subsequently calendered to the target density.

ARKEMA developed the SSE layer production, and it will be produced on the same coating line as the cathodes. Difficulties in processing the layers make it necessary to either produce self-standing membranes or to use a temporary support membrane (e.g. non-sticky foil).

The metallic lithium anodes will also be produced by a roll-to-roll process at ABEE. Micron-thick layers of lithium are deposited on copper substrate foil by thermal evaporation. To enhance the performance and increase the (electro-)chemical stability at the SSE-Li interface, an nm thick protective layer (ASEI) will be deposited on the lithium.

Cutting of the electrodes and SSE layer, as well as the stacking, will be done by automated systems to produce cell stacks, which are then contacted and packed in pouch foil.

The cost parameter quantified through MFCA showed that, for both 1 Ah and 10 Ah cells, the cathode production is the main contributor to the costs. In this step, the NMC811 and the catholyte are the major contributors, accounting for more than 40% and around 20-30% of the total costs, respectively, in both cases. In the case of the NMC811, its high contributions derive from the fact that these components contain CRMs, which generally have high prices. For the catholyte, its contribution is due to the high prices resulting from being an ionic liquid with a complex synthesis process and the need for high-purity materials for its production.

The 1 Ah and 10 Ah cells were quantified for five environmental parameters: global warming, fine particulate matter formation, mineral resource scarcity, fossil resource scarcity and water consumption.

In both cases, the electrolyte emerged as the main contributor to the environmental impacts, followed by the cathode, which was the second most significant contributor. The polymers were identified as the sole material driving the environmental impacts associated with the electrolyte. Within the cathode, the catholyte was the main contributor to global warming and fossil resource scarcity. NMC811 was the main contributor to fine particulate matter formation, mineral resource scarcity and water formation, ranging between 21-75%. The impact on the

anode was not as representative as the electrolyte and the cathode. This is related to the mass of the anode used in the cell, which was significantly lower than the electrolyte and the cathode. Please note that this analysis is focused exclusively on material contributions, not including energy consumption considerations during manufacturing and waste generation. It is important to highlight that the processes examined in this study were conducted at a laboratory scale. Consequently, the resulting economic and environmental parameters do not accurately reflect those of optimised industrial-scale operations. This limitation applies to the cell components (cathode, electrolyte, and anode) and the materials used, such as polymers and NMC811.

Optimising the overall cell manufacturing production can enhance its environmental performance, thereby improving the overall environmental impact of the electrolyte and cathode. Additionally, decreasing the consumption of both the polymers and NMC811 can further mitigate overall environmental impacts.

SSB cells need a certain amount of pressure to work properly, and the pressure should be constant and homogeneous during cycling in terms of pressure distribution. The application of such pressures, which are in the range of a few hundred kPa, can be realised by a metallic framework with a spring applying its force on two parallel plates in between the pouch cell. With the help of the other partners, TUBS developed these jigs based on their experience with similar setups by improving the existing concept. In total, 33 of the 1 Ah jigs have been produced and delivered to the partners.